

**MODIFICATION OF A MOTORIZED
ELECTRIC SCREW JACK FROM 2 TONS
TO 3.5 TONS CAPACITY**

BY

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MEE/18/8853

APPROVAL PAGE

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A

PROJECT

SUBMITTED TO

**THE DEPARTMENT OF MECHANICAL ENGINEERING,
SCHOOL OF ENGINEERING AND ENGINEERING
TECHNOLOGY**

FEDERAL UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY AKURE, NIGERIA

**IN PARTIAL FULFILMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR
THE AWARD OF POST GRADUATE DIPLOMA IN
MECHANICAL ENGINEERING**

DECEMBER, 2021

DECLARATION

I hereby declare that all the information furnished in this project report is based on my own intensive research and is genuine. This report does not, to the best of my knowledge, been submitted for the award of degree either of this university or any other university without proper citation.

Candidate's Name: Ogundeji, Olanrewaju Michael

Signature.....

Date.....

CERTIFICATION

I certify that this project report titled Modification of a Motorized Electric Screw Jack is the outcome of the research carried out by Ogundeji, Olanrewaju Michael with matriculation number MEE/18/8853 in the Department of Mechanical Engineering, Federal University of Technology, Akure.

Supervisor's Name.....

Signature.....

Date.....

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Last but not least, special thanks go to my beloved parents who supported me to reach my goals and sacrificed much in their life for my well-being. I also thank the educational websites from which I have taken help.

Thank you.

DEDICATION

This project is dedicated to Almighty God for sparing my life despite all.

ABSTRACT

An automotive jack is a piece of equipment used to raise all or part of a vehicle into the air in order to smoothen the progress of vehicle maintenance or breakdown repairs. The basic car jack is a very common piece of equipment known by most people and it is included as standard equipment for most new cars. Vehicle owners who would like to rotate their tyres themselves either from front to back and so forth or who may install snow tires before the winter and remove them in the spring need to use a jack to perform the job. Changing a flat tire is not a very enjoyable experience, especially without the help of a carjack.

This project was carried out using car battery power (12volts) to develop a motorized electric of carjack for emergency use. It examines the modification of the existing motor screw jack by integrating an electric motor in the screw jack so as to make load lifting a whole lot easier. The effective selection of using scissors for the design is the significance of its increased torque. The sole significance and purpose of this work are to alter the existing car jack in order to make the operation easier, safer and more reliable. The use of the modified carjack also helps to reduce health risks, especially backache problems which are associated with doing work in a bent or squatting position for a long period of time. The modified screw car jack is easy to use by pregnant women, old people or anybody. The improved design motorized jack also saves time and demands less human energy to operate. The design when adopted will efficiently curtail the problems associated with Ergonomics - which is a science that deals with designing and arranging things so that people can use them easily and safely. The screw car jack was tested and it has enough power to lift and hold the car as a normal car jack would.

CHAPTER ONE

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 PROJECT MOTIVATION

An automotive jack is an equipment used to raise all or part of a vehicle into the air in order to aid repairs. The basic car jack (manually operated) is a very common piece of equipment known by most people and it is included as standard equipment for most new cars. These days, a car jack is an essential tool in a vehicle due to it saving people from an unknown event such as a flat tire during our journeys. Even so, people who like to rotate their tires themselves or who would like to install snow tires before the winter and remove them in the spring need to use a jack for the task (American Lift Institute, 2004). Changing a flat tire is not a very enjoyable experience, especially without the help of a carjack.

Navy studies show that only 12% of women can achieve the two-person stretcher carry, a condition significant to ship security. Women may be able to drive a five-ton truck, but usually need a man's help to change a tire. Women have much lighter skeletons which means, among other things, they can't pull more force as well as men and are at greater risk of skeletal injuries. Typically, the car intentionally tries to get a flat tire at the least suitable moments. For example, times when you are rushing to work, going for something emergency, a business meeting or in the middle of the woods. To keep driving would be extremely difficult so the best option is to

remove the flat tyre and replace it with a spare. This is a time waster and it even endangers the person if the tyre is being changed in a hurry.

Working near a vehicle that is supported by a car jack can be deadly. In Nigeria, over the last four years, at least more than 25 people have been crushed and killed by a vehicle while they were working according to Punch Newspaper. All the deaths involved the vehicle being lifted or supported in the wrong way. Home mechanics are most at risk of this type of death or injury. In some cases the worker was killed when the vehicle was not secured by chocks and the vehicle rolled on top of them, or the structures used to support the vehicle failed. On average, 160 injuries are associated with car jacks each year. Injuries have ranged from amputation to fractures and crush injuries. The correct use of jacks can prevent death or injury. With the spare installed, you should be able to reach your house or the nearest service station.

Moreover, an organization named the American Lift Institute (ALI) was set up to promote improvements in automotive lift technology, especially in the area of safety. As recently as the late 1990s, car lift or jack manufacturers were permitted to affirm that their products were safe even though they did not meet any set standard. Appreciation to ALI's cooperative venture and the American National Standards Institute, every jack and lift must meet a set number of performance standards in order to be ALI/ANSI certified.

The automatic car jack really needs to be improved in order to make the tool more efficient, user-friendly and easy to use most significantly, with high safety features. Females, and old people will be able to use the improved automatic (electric) car jack with little or no help.

1.2 BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

During the repair and maintenance of automobiles (vehicles), it is usually a necessity to lift a vehicle to change a tyre or to access the underside of the automobile. For that reason, a variety of car jacks have been developed for lifting an automobile from a ground surface. Available car jacks, however, are normally manually operated and thus, they need considerable arduous physical effort on the part of the user. Such jacks are difficult for the elderly and handicapped and are especially detrimental under unpleasant weather conditions.

Furthermore, existing jacks are usually large, heavy and also not easy to keep, carry or move into the appropriate location under an automobile. Also, jacks are generally not modified to be readily disbanded and stored after automobile repairs have been completed.

In light of such inherent disadvantages, commercial automobile repair and service stations are commonly equipped with large and hi-tech car lifts, in which such lifts are raised and lowered via electrically-powered systems. However, due to their size and high costs of purchasing and maintaining electrically-powered car lifts are not available to the average car owner. Such

electrical-powered portable jacks not only remove the laborious task of lifting an automobile via manually-operated jacks but also reduce the time required to repair the automobile. Such a characteristic can be particularly beneficial when it is required to repair an automobile on the side of a roadway or under other perilous conditions.

There are reports of car jacks that it leads to a grave number of accidents. These are due to the fact that safety features that are on usual car jacks are not enough. A specific jack is purported to hold up to 1000 kilograms, but tests undertaken by Consumer Affairs have revealed that it fails to work after lifting 250 kilograms and may physically break when it has a weight close to its 1000 kilograms capacity. Even as no injuries have been reported to date, Ms Rankine has expressed concern about the dangers associated with the use of a vehicle jack that does not carry the weight it is promoted to hold.

1.3 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Existing jacks offer a lot of difficulties for the elderly, and women and are especially detrimental under unfavorable weather conditions. These presently available jacks additionally involve the operator remaining in the prolonged bent or squatting position to operate the jack. Doing work in a bent or squatting position for a long period of time is not easy for people. In addition, the safety features on the present jack are also not enough for the operator to use, mainly because it does not have a lock or extra beam to withstand the massive load of the car. This is for safety precaution in case the screw break.

Furthermore, available jacks are usually big, weighty and also difficult to keep, carry or move into the proper position under an automobile. Suppose car jacks are easy to use for pregnant or whoever had a problem with the tires in the middle of nowhere stress would be reduced. The purpose of this project is to solve these problems. An electric car jack which has a frame type of design by using electricity from the car lighter will be developed. The operator only needs to press the button from the controller without working in a bent or squatting position for a long period of time to change the tires.

1.4 AIM OF THE RESEARCH

The aim of this research is to modify a motorized electrical screw jack of an average capacity of 2.0 tons to be able to raise and sustain a load of more than 2.0 tons.

1.5 OBJECTIVES OF THE RESEARCH

The specific objectives of this work are to:

- Identify the needs and design requirements for a motorized electrical screw jack
- Carry out design and stress analysis of the component parts of a CAD model designed of a motorized electrical screw jack.

- Fabricate the designed CAD model, carry out test and performance evaluation of the fabricated motorized electrical screw jack.

1.6 SCOPE

The scope of this project is to modify an existing motorized electric screw jack with a capacity of 2.0 tons load to be able to carry more load. The design is incorporated with an electrical cord using internal car power. The developed motorized electrical car jack was connected to a car

1.7 JUSTIFICATION

The existing manual jack has been a problem to the user because it requires energy sapping and time wasting. Therefore, old men and women and indeed everybody using the jack can easily plug the cord into the vehicle and thereby address the issue of stress.

1.8 EXPECTED CONTRIBUTION OF THE RESEARCH TO KNOWLEDGE

The expected contribution to knowledge is that the work will give a different means of isolating the prime mover from the screw jack and provide housing for the device in order to prevent the transmission system from dust and corrosion.

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Jack Definition.

A jack is a mechanical lifting device used to apply great forces or lift loads. A mechanical jack employs a screw thread for lifting heavy equipment. A device for lifting the vehicle, or part of the vehicle, off the ground to facilitate repairs. The most common jacks are the bumper, tripod, scissors, and hydraulic jacks.

Mechanical jacks are typically rated for a maximum lifting capacity of 1.5 tons or 3 tons. More powerful jacks use hydraulic power to provide more lift over greater distances and can be rated for many tons of loads.

2.1.2 Electric Car Jack

The electrically operated jack is the modified jack. It is simple to handle and operate. It is operated by a car battery which makes it very comfortable for users, especially old people and for women.

An electric car jack includes a base frame or housing that is modified to be placed on the ground underneath the automobile to be lifted. The housing includes motors connected to drive arms connected to a load bridge and plate. The bridge is typically mounted within the drive arms by rods located within slots on the arms enabling the bridge to move upward and downward while being retained within the drive arms. The drive arms typically include drive wheels that rotate and are joined together by a chain mechanism that assures the coupler moves unvaryingly.

In general, the motors are operated by the car's battery. The drive from the motor is transferred to the worm and worm gear which are connected ahead to the driver gear.

This driver gear operates the driven gear by spur gear arrangement mechanism. In this way motors drive the arms, lifting and lowering the load bridge which lifts and lowers the automobile.

Below are some of the advantages of the modified (electric) car jack,

- 1) Extremely low maintenance required.
- 2) Self-contained mechanism with compact design.
- 3) Robust.
- 4) Shock absorbent and silent

2.2 Historical background

During World War 2, screw-type jacks were usually in use and very common for trucks and jeeps. The jacks with wedge mechanisms were introduced in Nigeria because they can't afford high-priced Jack since most cars sent to Nigeria are mostly together with normal manual screw Jack, especially for both small and medium-sized vehicles (Ademola and Sunday, 2008). There is evidence of the use of screws in the Ancient world but it was the great Leonardo who first gives the design of a screw jack for lifting loads. Leonardo da Vinci's design used a threaded worm gear, propped up on bearings that are rotated by the turning of a worm shaft to drive a lifting screw to move the load (Chuka and Chinwuko. 2014).

The most distinguished inventor in mechanical engineering was mechanical engineer Joseph Whitworth, who found the need for precision had become an important part in industry. There is design-based 3D software Pro/E with an 8m high scissors lift platform, The platform is designed to be folded away behind doors, to save more space for convenient storage (Tianllongyu *et al.*, 201 1). The idea of using a screw as a machine element was given by Archimedes in 250 BC, with his device used for pumping water. In 2011, a paper was published in which an author used a toggle damper brace system to calculate and analyze installation 1110dcs and experiments conducted to improve and understand the influence of

key factors and to provide design guidance (Zhang, 2011). A new version of the ball-bearing screw jack was introduced by Duff Company.

A modified version of the motor Screw jack has been launched by using an electric motor in the Screw to make load lifting easier (Akinwonmi and Mohammed, 2012). In 1930, the First worn gear screw jack that is instantly identifiable was found. In the Toggle jack, diverse pairs of screws and nuts have been used to get induce stresses within the safe limit under the loading condition from 1 kN to 5kN (Patal, 2013). With the ability to be linked mechanically and driven by either air or electric motors, the first model had a lifting capacity of 10 tons with a raise of 4 inch.

A new design with a new methodology and an effort was made to manufacture a new design that can produce greater capacity within the economic range (Ranglani, 2014). Today, screw jacks can be connected mechanically and also electronically and with the advances in motion control, loads can be situated to any small unit like microns. Upgrading in gear technology mutually with the addition of precision ball and roller screws means the applications for screw jacks today are endless and are real. The new type of jack is operated by using the power of car battery (Udgirkar and Patil, 2014). Various Developments in Lifting Devices are screw threads, hydraulics, wheels and axles. A screw jack which uses a motor is now referred to as a linear actuator which is basically still a screw jack.

A range of malfunctions has also taken place in the jacks due to diverse stresses induced in the jack (Dhamak *et al.*, 2015). The calculation made in this paper is used to lessen the cost of jack by using two dissimilar sections of three different materials and comparing which is best appropriate to lessen the cost with a high strength-to-weight ratio. In the case of a jack, a small force applied in its horizontal plane is used to elevate or lower a large load. We use Double start square thread as it is very strong and can resist the large loads imposed on most scissors jacks while not being weakened by wear over many rotations.

2.2.1 Scissor Carjack

Scissor car jacks usually use mechanical advantage to allow a human to lift a vehicle by manual force using long, self-locking jack screws to raise the vehicle. Although these jacks are simply designed, they are considered so strong and reliable that car manufacturers frequently include them with new cars, according to Floor Automotive Jacks.

The centrally located jack screw raises and lowers the scissor-shaped jack using either a tire iron or a specially designed tool. These jacks differ in size and weight-bearing capabilities, so one has to be careful when buying one (Pawar. *et al.*, 2015}

Plate 2.1 Scissor Carjack (*International Journal of Mechanical and Industrial Engineering*

(*IJWE*). 1(2) 2231 -6477.)

2.2.2 Bottle car jack

This type of jack has a power screw that can alter the rotary motion to a linear motion. This type of jack is very flexible and can not only help lift vehicles but can also help in pushing vehicles around. These jacks are compact in size but are designed and built for performance. Lifting capacity ranges from heavy-duty 1-ton bottle jack up to 30-ton bottle jack (Pawar *et al*, 2015).

Plate 2.2 Bottle carjack (*Shutterstock.com*)

2.2.3 Hydraulic Bottle Carjack

This type of automotive jack uses hydraulics to supply adequate force to raise a vehicle weighing up to several tons. Most hydraulic jacks have a cylinder, top, base, plunger and pump filled with oil. Using the plunger builds oil pressure, which is controlled by valves, and performs the lifting and lowering actions. These jacks are rated according to how much weight they can safely lift without failing. Olive-Drab reports lower end hydraulic jacks can lift up to 3 tons without problem (Pawar *et al*, 2015).

Plate 2.3 Hydraulic Bottle Carjack (*Shutterstock.com*)

2.2.4 Trolley Carjack

A trolley jack above is a type of wheeled hydraulic floor jack that can easily be moved.

Depending on the size and weight of a vehicle, standard trolley jacks can lift weights ranging

from 2 to 4 tons. While some models have characteristics such as manual braking controls,

others have brakes that lock automatically when the jack is being used. Unlike other jacks that

may trip or unfasten unless on a firm surface, a trolley jack can be safely used on gravel or dirt

and will lift the vehicle higher (Pawar *et al.* 2015)

Plate 2.4 Trolley Carjack ((*Shutterstock.com*))

2.2.5 Pneumatic Carjack

A pneumatic jack above is a hydraulic jack that is activated by compressed air - for example, air from a compressor - instead of human work. This eradicates the need for the user to activate the hydraulic mechanism, reducing effort and potentially increasing speed. Sometimes, such jacks are also able to be operated by the normal hydraulic actuation method, thereby retaining functionality, even if a source of compressed air is not available. Hydraulic jacks, on the other hand, use liquid to affect motion. Both types of jacks are available to consumers; however, hydraulic jacks are more popular for a number of reasons, and pneumatic jacks are less readily available due to the drawbacks of pneumatic mechanics. This doesn't mean that a pneumatic jack

is a terrible option, but rather that a comparison between the two products is time well spent (Pawar *et al.*, 2015).

Plate 2.5 Pneumatic Carjack (*Shutterstock.com*)

2.2.6 Electrical Carjack

An electric car jack is a device that plugs into the 12V lighter or power socket on your car which can be used in place of a manual jack if you need to change a tire or raise your car to work on the undercarriage

An electric car jack uses a motor to raise your vehicle. As the jack's motor runs, the jack turns, raises and lifts the car. An electric jack creates less force per turn than a manual jack, but it turns

at a much faster rate. Most electric car jacks have a 12-foot power cord to place the jack at any corner of the car, and will raise an I-ton vehicle up to 14 inches (Pawar *et al.*, 2015).

Classifications of jack in general depend on the type of work or load to be performed on the vehicles and variable load it carries. Stephen *et al* 2015, work on experimental investigation of performance of laboratory screw jack using the mechanical advantage, velocity ratio and mechanical efficiency of the machine obtained at different loads. This is a prototype useful in the mechanics of machine laboratory of the department of mechanical engineering for practical exercise. After eight successive experiments were completed at various loads with pitch of the screw thread constant, it was established that the relationship between the load and efficiency, and between the load and effort applied is linear, it was also revealed that reduction in load means reduction in effort and reduction in load which in turn causes an increase in efficiency.

Nitinchandra *et al.*, 2013, worked on the design of toggle jack considering material selection of screw-nut combination. Toggle jack is a device which lifts heavy equipment. In their work, the toggle jack was designed analytically. Screw and nut are the most important part, and the design is based on the utmost tensile stress and maximum shear stress. Their result shows that the alloy steel and phosphorus bronze for nut is the best suitable combination.

Anish et al., 2011 worked on engine operated screw jack, this device uses only the engine power to raise the car in any topography and altitude. An engine was chosen for this reason to work on and its characteristics were studied. They got the following results: it proves that the device will be a success upon installation on any type of vehicle. Even heavy duty vehicles like trucks, lorry, and buses can be lifted with low maintenance, the initial cost is also low when regarding its use. It requires it to be set up once and so no repeated cost is needed at the time of puncture. They concluded that, the performance of this device can be extended by using sensors. The sensors can be used to sense the punctured wheel and aid the function of device from the driver seat itself. This will increase the scope of the device.

Ivan *et al.*, 2014, worked on the design and fabrication of motorized automated object lifting jack. Investigation conducted in this regard revealed that in several automobile garages, some complicated methods were used in lifting the vehicles for reconditioning, repair and maintenance. This fabricated model has mainly concentrated on this difficulty, and hence a suitable device has been designed, such that the vehicle and heavy objects can be lifted from floor land without the application of impact force. The automated motorized object lifting jack has been designed in such a way that it can be used to lift the vehicle very effortlessly without any impact force. The operation is made straightforward so that even unskilled labor can use it with ease. The D.C motor is attached with the lead screw by gear arrangement, the lead screw

rotation depends upon the rotation of D.C motor. This is an era of automation where it is broadly defined as replacement of manual effort by mechanical power in all degrees of automation.

Gaurav et al., 2014, worked on design, development and analysis of electrically operated toggle jack using the power of a car battery. Their paper analyze the alteration of the current toggle jack by incorporating an electric DC motor in the screw so as to make load lifting easier for emergency use with using power of car batter (12 Volts). Gear ratio is used to boost the lifting power. The importance and purpose is to transform the existing car jack in order to make the operation easier, safer and more dependable in order to save individual internal energy and lessen health risks especially back ache problems associated with doing work in a bent or squatting position for a long period of time. The car jack is developed using CATIA V5R19 and analyzed using Finite Element Analysis to check safety factor and force acting. Furthermore the torque supplied on the system is more than enough to lift a car weight around 1200 kg.

Jaideep and Dilshad, (2016), focused on Designing and Calculating the Stresses Induced in Scissors Jack for Three Different Materials. To reduce the cost of jack they have taken two different sections of three different materials i.e. Mild Steel, AISI 1045 grade Steel, GS-52.3 Cast Steel and comparing which will be suitable for the above mentioned function. By using these materials, calculation and comparison of the Strength to weight ratio and find which material is best suited for high load carrying capacity with minimum failure or deformation was

achieved. They concluded that out of three materials AISI 1045 graded Steel is also good for carrying maximum load but in comparison to mild steel it is more.

Sathiyaraj *et al.*, (2015), paid attention to the design and fabrication of pneumatic jack for automobiles. The main objective of the project is to fabricate an improved version of a mini pneumatic jack. This will be more efficient for the user. This machine is pneumatic powered which has low co-efficient of friction and it requires no other means of power to operate.. A pneumatic cylinder erected provides power to lift up the Jack. The essential components are Compressor, Pneumatic cylinder, Solenoid, Control circuit and Jack. The working medium adopted is compressed air. The compressed air is transmitted through tubes to pneumatic cylinder where power is converted into reciprocating motion. The reciprocating motion is obtained by using an electrically controlled solenoid valve. The input to the solenoid valve is given through the control unit. The reciprocating motion transmitted to the jack through the piston which moves on the cylinder. The jack is placed under the vehicle chassis, where the vehicle is to be lifted. The vehicle can be lifted when the solenoid valve is switched on. The vehicle over the jack gets the reciprocating motion through the piston which is connected to the jack. Thus, using a pneumatic jack, the vehicle can be lifted with ease in operation.

Table 2.1: Summary of the Review

S/N	AUTHOR(S)	CONTRIBUTION	YEAR
1	Stephen Tamberi <i>et al</i>	Experimental Investigation of the performance of laboratory screw jack using the mechanical advantage, velocity ratio and mechanical efficiency of machine obtained at different loads	2015
2	Moksh Patel, Karnav Gajjar, Shiv Goud and Guarang Parmar	Review of an electrical car jack used in an automobile	2018
3	Jithendra Kumar Repalle	Automatic Scissor Jack Using Car Battery	2017
4	Manish Kumar <i>et al</i>	Electrical Car Jack	2015

5	Nitinchandra <i>et al</i>	Design of Toggle Jack considering the material selection of screw nut combination	2013
6	Ivan <i>et al</i>	Design and Fabrication of motorized automated object lifting Jack	2014
7	Manoj and Kachave	Design and analysis of Scissor Jack	2015
8	Adegunloye, Joseph Bamidele	Development of Motorized Electric Screw Jack for 2 tons Capacity	2019

CHAPTER THREE

3.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study takes into consideration the design and fabrication of an electrically powered screw jack. A stress analysis was done by using Autodesk Inventor in order to analyze the stress induced in the components of the jack when carrying different loads.

To simplify the methodology, a flow chat will be used to represent the start-to-finish activities of the electrically powered screw jack. It shows how the goal of the project is being approached.

Figure 3.1: Research Methodology Flowchart

3.1 Description of Electrically Powered Screw Jack.

A power screw is a mechanical device used for converting rotary motion into linear motion and transmitting power. A power screw is also called translation screw. It uses helical translatory motion of the screw thread in transmitting power rather than clamping the machine components.

The screw jack is basically made up of metallic links connected together with pins and supported by base plates.

A horizontally positioned screw thread shaft which passes through the center is turned by torque from the gear drive and passes through the center of the links. The screw thread shaft is supported in bearings at both ends of the link in order to aid the transmission of power from the gear drive to the links. The gear is powered by a 12 volts DC motor and it uses the energy gained from the automobile vehicle battery that will be lifted.

Two gears will be mounted, one at the motor shaft and the other at screw jack rotary part. Metal plate will be used as the base where the motor and the jack will be fixed and the teeth of the gears will mesh perfectly with the special arrangement that will be put in place. When the motor is powered and the screw rotates clock wisely, the jack will then raise up the load and when it is controlled to rotate counterclockwise, the jack will drop the load at the control speed.

Pictorial view, orthographic and sectional view of the screw jack are presented in the figures below,

Figure 3.2: Pictorial View of the Automated Screw Jack

Figure 3.3: Sectional View of the Motorized Screw Jack

Figure 3.4: Exploded View of the Designed Electric Screw Jack

Figure 3.5: A base plate of The Electric Screw Jack

Figure 3.6: Bearing Bushing of the Electric Screw Jack

3.2 Materials

Some components to be used, are:

- i. Lead screw
- ii. 12 V D.C. Battery
- iii. 12 V D.C. Motor
- iv. Control Switches
- v. Rigid base Cigarette lighter receptacle- component of the vehicle

vi. Control Cables.

3.2.1. Lead Screw

The lead screw is used as a linkage in a machine to turn motion into linear motion. The size and shape (i.e. short, tall, fat & thin) of the lead screw depends on the load under the work and the space in which they need to fit. Due to the sliding contact of the lead screw, a large amount of heat is generated. To overcome such problems and to increase efficiency it should be worked under ambient conditions or lubricant must be applied.

3.2.2. DC Motor

It is a machine which converts electrical energy into mechanical energy. It works on the principle of electromagnetic induction i.e., when a current-carrying conductor is placed in a magnetic field it experiences a magnetic force whose direction is given by the Fleming's right-hand rule. The main advantage of a DC motor is that its direction of rotation can be changed by changing the polarity of the power supply.

3.2.3. Control Switch

This is the switch used to operate the DC motor by which the entire operation of the jack is to be controlled. The commonly used switch is Toggle Switch. This switch is manually actuated by a mechanical lever. These switches are designed in such a way that it can operate multiple sets of electrical contacts.

3.2.4. Control Cables

These cables are used to provide electrical connection to various parts of the system with the battery.

3.2.5. Base and frame

It is a rigid construction on which all the parts are assembled.

3.2.6 Research Analysis of Component parts of the Crew Jack

The materials and methods adopted in this research considered the following factors. These factors are,

- i. Availability of materials
- ii. Mechanical Properties of the material selected (Rigidity, Corrosion, and wear resistance)
- iii. Overall weight of the electric screw jack
- iv. Cost of fabrication
- v. Maximum and minimum capacity of the screw jack
- vi. Machine positioning and rigidity
- vii. Ergonomics
- viii. Material Selection
- ix. Power consumption
- x. Enclosure for the device and choice of casing material

3.2.7 Screw Thread.

The screw thread is responsible for the production of the turning action that is needed by the nuts to lift or pull the arms of the jack. The screw thread is supported at both ends by nuts which convert its turning action to translational motion of the arms joint. It receives its power from the DC motor via the gear arrangement. A little consideration will show that the maximum load on the screw thread occurs when the jack is carrying a load and it is in a lower position. As the jack pushes the load, the load carried by the screw thread reduces and it is transferred to the arms. (Khurmi and Gupta, 2009).

3.3 Calculations for Torque, Effort required and Efficiency using 1 ton

Let the jack have a capacity of 1 ton and the load acting on the jack is of $\frac{1}{4}$ of a total load of the vehicle.

Therefore, load acting on one wheel is from 300 to 500 kg, for safety consideration the load is assumed to be 400 Kg.

$$\text{Load (W)} = 400 \text{ Kg} = 4000 \text{ N}$$

$$\text{Major Screw Diameter (d}_o\text{)} = 12 \text{ mm}$$

$$\text{Pitch of Screw (p)} = 3 \text{ mm}$$

$$\text{Mean diameter (dm)} = d_o - \left(\frac{p}{2}\right)$$

$$= 12 - \left(\frac{3}{2}\right) = 10.5 \text{ mm}$$

Lead (l) = pitch (p) = 3 mm (Since screw is single star)

Let,

$$\text{Lead angle } (\alpha) \tan\alpha = \left(\frac{l}{\pi dm}\right)$$

$$\tan\alpha = \frac{3}{\pi * 10.5}$$

$$\tan\alpha = 0.091$$

Assume coefficient of friction (μ) = 0.1

Load to be raise = 400 Kg = 4000 N

P = Effort required to raise the load

$$P = W * \tan(\alpha + \theta)$$

$$P = W * \left(\frac{\tan\alpha + \tan\theta}{1 - (\tan\alpha * \tan\theta)}\right)$$

$$P = 4000 * \left(\frac{0.091 + 0.1}{1 - (0.091 * 0.1)}\right)$$

$$P = 771.01 \text{ N}$$

Torque required for operating the screw,

$$T = P * \left(\frac{dm}{2} \right)$$

$$T = 771.01 * \left(\frac{10.5}{2} \right)$$

$$T = 4047.83 \text{ Nmm}$$

$$T = 4.047 \text{ Nm}$$

Power required to drive the motor $P = T * \omega$

$$P = 4.047 * \left(\frac{2\pi N}{60} \right)$$

$$P = 4.047 * \left(2\pi * \frac{60}{60} \right) \dots \text{(Since } N=60 \text{ rpm)}$$

$$P = 25.433 \text{ W}$$

Since the speed of revolution is 60 rpm then the feed per min is

$$N = \left(\frac{x}{\text{pitch}} \right)$$

Where x = feed per min.

$$60 = \left(\frac{x}{3} \right)$$

$$x = 180 \frac{\text{mm}}{\text{min}}$$

The efficiency of screw calculated by using torque equation

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\tan \alpha}{\tan(\alpha + \theta)}$$

$$\varepsilon = \frac{0.091}{0.192}$$

$$\varepsilon = 47.36 \%$$

STRESSES ACTING ON VARIOUS COMPONENTS

1. Torsion stress acting on power screw.

$$\tau_{\max} \geq \frac{T}{J} j = \frac{\pi d^3}{32}$$

τ_{\max} = max torsional stress
T = Torque
d = screw diameter

2. Buckling load acting on lifting frame.

$$\frac{W}{A} \leq C \pi^2 \frac{A}{\left(\frac{L}{K}\right)^2}$$

W = axial load on frames
L = length of frame
C = 1 for long columns
K = radius of gyration

3. Yielding stress acting on lifting frame.

$$\sigma^T \leq \frac{S_y}{n}$$

σ^T = yielding stress
 S_y = endurance limit
n = Factor of safety

4. Bearing stress acting on rivets.

$$\sigma_p \leq \frac{S_y}{n}$$

σ_p = yielding stress
 S_y = endurance limit
 n = Factor of safety

5. Shear stress acting on rivets

$$\tau \leq .577S_y/n$$

S_y = endurance limit
 n = Factor of safety

τ = shear stress

6. Bending stress acting on coupling joints.

$$\sigma = \frac{m * d}{I_x}$$

$$I_x = \frac{\pi(R^4 - r^4)}{4}$$

I_x = polar moment of inertia
 R = outer radius
 r = inner radius
 m = bending moment

3.5 Possible Failure or Error:

A. Unstable center of gravity

B. Noise due to vibration (material used for the gear can be improved on)

C. Jack failure due to excess mass being lifted (>4tons)

D. Failure of primary bolts due to bending moments and shear stresses.

3.6 Cost Analysis for production of The Motorized Screw Jack

The cost estimate for production of the jack is represented in the Table below;

S/N	PARTS/COMPONENTS	AMOUNT (N)
1	Manual Jack	30,000
2	DC Motor	65,000
3	Control Switch	5,000
4	Relay	3,500
5	Connectors	3,000
6	Casing Fabrication	10,000
7	Gear Machining	5,000
8	Cable	3,000
9	Miscellaneous	5,000
	Total	<u>129,500</u>

CHAPTER FOUR

4.0 Performance evaluation of the Fabricated Screw Jack

The performance review of the modified electric screw jack was evaluated by testing it with different vehicles of different weight ranging from 2 tons to 4 tons. To carry out the test, the jack was firstly run with no load in order to ascertain its functionality. The figures below represent the pictorial evidence of the fabricated jack with testing and performance. The weight of the vehicle as specified by the manufacturer was noted and the effort was determined in each of the equation used in the write up.

(Pallet 4.1) Former design of Motorized carjack capacity 2.0 using Bevel Gear

(Pallet 4.2) New Design of Motorized Carjack of 3.5 tons using spur gear

The distance moved by the effort is measured from the length of screw extending out of the arms of the jack when it has lifted the load.

4.1 Discussion of Results

From the result obtained, it can be deduced that the Motorized jack can lift a load of up to 4 tons compared to the previous jack of just 2 tons. It is also important to note that the modified Motorized Jack can lift the load and as well sustain it. Though spur gear arrangement was used instead of the bevel gear used in the previous design in order to be

able to sustain the load effectively. The material used for the gear designed was also reviewed to be iron and not Teflon, this will give the required strength and ruggedness needed to get the maximum efficiency of the Motorized Jack.

CHAPTER FIVE

5.0 CONCLUSION

Electric Car Jacks are the ideal product to push, pull, lift, lower and position loads of anything from a couple of kilograms to hundreds of tons. Their need has long existed for an improved portable jack for automotive vehicles.

It is highly desirable that a jack become available that can be operated alternatively from inside the vehicle or from a location of safety off the road on which the vehicle is located.

Such a jack should desirably be light enough and be compact enough so that it can be stored in an automobile trunk, can be lifted up and carried by most adults to its position of use, and yet be capable of lifting a wheel of more than 2 tons vehicle off the ground.

Furthermore, it should be stable and easily controllable by a switch so that jacking can be done from a position of safety.

It should be easily movable either to a position underneath the axle of the vehicle or some other reinforced support surface designed to be engaged by a jack. Thus, the product has

been developed considering all the above requirements. This particular design of the electric Car jack will prove to be beneficial in lifting and lowering of loads

5.1 Recommendation

It is recommended that;

- More research work should be done on this topic (Design and Fabrication of a Motorized Jack)
- The Jack can be designed and developed to suit the present day technology advancement with the use of remote control and probably incorporating the control on an mobile application that can run on both Android and IOS.
- Mass production of this design can be looked into in order to make life easier for human everybody.
- It should also be noted that modification can still be made on this Project e.g different gear arrangement options can be explored to achieve the same aim.

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